

SPORTS BRAND AWARENESS: A STUDY AMONG THE STUDENTS OF THE JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY

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Abstract:

India is the country with the largest youth population of the world. Almost 356 million people in the age group of 10-24 years live in India. A major part of this youth population is extremely aware of the branded products, including sports brands. According to a report of the Confederation of Indian Industries (CII), the sports equipment market of India for the year 2013 was INR 40 billion with cricket equipment holding the largest market share. The objective of this paper was to study the sports brand awareness among this youth. A group of fifty students were selected from the Jadavpur University, Kolkata on a random sampling method to conduct the survey. The results clearly show that the sports brand awareness of the respondents is above average.

Key Words: Sports, brand, respondents, products, awareness, students & Jadavpur University

Introduction:

A brand is usually defined as a product or service or concept which is markedly different from other products, services and concept so that it can easily be communicated and marketed. Branding can be defined as the unique design, sign, symbol, words, or a combination of these, employed in creating an image that identifies a product and differentiates it from its competitors. Awareness is the ability to directly know and perceive, to feel, or to be conscious of events, objects, thoughts, emotions or any other sensory patterns. The objective of this paper was to study the sports brand awareness among the students of the Jadavpur University.

Methodology:

The data of this study were collected from the primary sources. The primary data was collected through a well-defined questionnaire. The questionnaires were validated by the two other assistant professor of the department of Physical Education. Fifty (50) students age ranging from 21-26yrs. of the Jadavpur University were selected on the basis of random sampling methodology for the purpose of the study.

Limitations of the Study:

Followings are the limitations of the study:

- ✓ This research work covered only the students of the Jadavpur University.
- ✓ The researchers did not want the personal information of the respondent.

Result and Discussion:

At the very outset, attempt has been made to define the profile of the respondents. Table 1 represents the profile of the respondents.

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

Details		Frequency (N)	Percentage of Population
Gender	Male	35	70%
	Female	15	30%
Age	Between 21-25	40	80%
	Between 25-30	10	20%
Next academic target	M. P. Ed	12	24%
	Ph.D.	2	4%
	NET	4	8%
	SSC	20	40%
	Others	18	36%
Playing Time	1-3hour	45	90%
	3-5hour	5	10%

The following table represents the sports brand awareness in various categories of the students of the Jadavpur University:

Table 2: Sports brand awareness of the students of the Jadavpur University

Shoes	%	Boots	%	Racket	%	Balls	%
Adidas	70	Adidas	75	Adidas	60	Adidas	70
Nike	65	Nike	70	Yonex	55	Nike	65
Yonex	60	Puma	60	Cosco CBX	60	Puma	60
Others	50	Others	45	Others	65	Others	50
Average	61	Average	62	Average	60	Average	61

Diagram 1-4 represents the sports brand awareness of the students of the Jadavpur University in a graphical format.

Diagram 1-4: Sports brand awareness of the students of the Jadavpur University

Diagram 1: Brand Awareness for Shoes

Diagram 2: Brand Awareness for Boots

Diagram 3: Brand Awareness for Rackets

Diagram 4: Brand Awareness for Balls

It can be concluded from the above table and diagrams that the average sports brand awareness of the respondents of the J.U. Student is 61% in case of sports shoe, 62% in case of boot, 60 % in case of racket and 61% in case of ball. The following table represents the ranking of the sports brands. This ranking is made on the basis of the awareness of the students of the Jadavpur University.

Table 2: Ranking of the Sports Brands

Shoes		Boots		Rackets		Balls	
Category	Rank	Category	Rank	Category	Rank	Category	Rank
Addidas	1	Nike	1	Adidas	1	Adidas	1
Nike	2	Adidas	2	Yonex	2	Nike	2
S.G.	3	Speeds	3	Cosco	3	Puma	3
Yonex	4	Puma	4	Wilson	4	Lotto	4
Others	5	Others	5	Others	5	Others	5

It can be concluded from the above table that in case of shoe category, rank 1, 2, 3 and 4 are given to Adidas, Nike, S.G. and Yonex respectively. Other brands are given ranking 5. In case of Boots 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th 5th ranks are given to the Nike, Adidas, speeds, Puma and others brand respectively. In case of Rcket respondents have given 1st rank to Adidas, 2nd to Yonex, 3rd to Cosco, 4th to Wilson. In case of Balls 1st rank is given to the Adidas, 2nd is given to the Nike, 3rd to the Puma, 4th to the Lotto. Table 3 represents the level of satisfaction of the respondents after using the sports brands.

Table 3: Level of Satisfaction

Subjects	Satisfied (%)	Dissatisfied (%)
Product	90%	10%
Product price range	70%	30%
If the price of this brand increase	50%	50%

From the above table, it can be said that 90% of the respondents are satisfied with the quality of the products, while 10% are dissatisfied. 70% of them are satisfied with the price range of the products, while 30% are not satisfied. 50% have confirmed that they still prefer to buy the same product if the price range increases. However, 50% may not purchase the same brand if the price of the products will increase. The following table represents the mediums that make them aware of the sports products.

Table 4: Mediums that make the respondents aware of the sports brand

Factors	Percentage (%)	Rank
Television	70%	1
Internet	20%	2
Newspaper	9%	3
Road Banner	1%	4

70% of the respondents have said that television makes them aware of the sports brands, while 20%, 9% and 1% of the respondents have confirmed that internet, newspaper and road banners respectively are the mediums of their brand awareness. The mediums of brand awareness are represented in the following diagram.

Diagram 5: Mediums of brand awareness

Results and Discussion:

The results of the study are concluded in the following section:

- ✓ The average awareness of the respondents of the students of the Jadavpur University is above average in case of the sports products, i.e. shoes, boots, rackets and balls.
- ✓ In case of Shoe, respondents have given the 1st rank to Adidas, 2nd to Nike, 3rd to Yonex. In case of Boots 1st, 2nd, 3rd ranks are given to Adidas, Nike and Puma respectively. In case of Rackets, 1st rank is given to Adidas, 2nd is to Yonex and 3rd to Cosco. In case of Balls respondents reported 1st rank to Adidas, 2nd to Nike, 3rd to Puma.
- ✓ The brand awareness of Adidas and Nike is higher than any other brand.
- ✓ Television plays an important role in making people aware of the sports brands. The roles of internet and newspapers are also crucial for providing information about the brands.
- ✓ Majority of the users are happy with the quality of the products and the prices. However, half of the users may shift the brand if there will be an increase in price.

Conclusion:

The awareness of the sports brand among the students of the Jadavpur University is above average. Most of the students use branded products with the belief that these products deliver better quality than non-branded products. It has been observed that there is an increasing trend of using branded sports products among the students of the Jadavpur University, which is also a result of their modern lifestyle.

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